

On Phthalide Formation.

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Prior to the observation of Perkin that formaldehyde condenses directly with *m*-methoxy-benzoic acid derivatives in presence of concentrated hydrochloric acid (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 197) to yield phthalide, there was the Fritsch reaction (*Annalen*, 1897, 296, 344; 1898, 301, 352), a very round about way of synthesising similarly constituted compounds.

The present investigation was undertaken with a view to effect a synthesis of cotarnic acid and myristicinic acid methyl ester was subjected to the Fritsch reaction, but the methylene-dioxy group was found to be unstable towards 90% sulphuric acid, and Perkin's method of phthalide formation also led to unworkable tarry products. Perkin's method as modified by Roy and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1621) was next tried, but the reaction product from both gallic acid trimethyl ether and myristicinic acid was chloromethyl phthalide (I).

The chloromethyl phthalide derivatives gave with potassium cyanide in alcoholic solution the respective cyanomethyl phthalides which on hydrolysis gave the corresponding phenyl acetic acid derivatives.

But if in place of glacial acetic acid used by Roy and Robinson in their modification of Perkin's method, water be used simple phthalides are obtained and the phthalide, thus obtained from gallic acid trimethyl ether, was found to be identical with that described by Meldrum (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 964). The phthalide obtained from myristicinic acid may have either of the structures (II) and (III), but owing to the failure of the oxidation experiments the constitution of the product could not be settled.

In conclusion, it may be remarked that *m*-methoxy-benzoic acid derivatives, having an additional *p*-orienting group chiefly the methoxyl, yield by Roy and Robinson's method chloromethyl phthalide provided the *p*-position to the additional methoxyl group is free.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Gallic Acid Series.

3 : 4 : 5-*Trimethoxy-2-chloromethylphthalide*.—Gallic acid trimethyl ether (10 g.), glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.), fuming hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) and 40% formaldehyde solution (12.5 c.c.) were heated under reflux on a steam-bath for 3-4 hours, when the reaction mixture turned deep brown. The reaction product was precipitated by diluting the reaction mixture with a large volume of water, filtered, washed with water and treated with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, when the unreacted acid dissolved leaving the chloromethyl phthalide derivative as an almost colourless powder. It crystallises in colourless needles, m.p. 86°. (Found: Cl, 12.86; OMe, 33.6. $C_{12}H_{13}O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 13.02; OMe, 34.12 per cent).

3 : 4 : 5-*Trimethoxy-2-cyanomethylphthalide*.—The above compound (5.5 g.) was heated with potassium cyanide (1.6 g.) and alcohol (4 c.c.) on a steam-bath under reflux for 4 hours, when the reaction was complete. The reaction product was obtained by diluting the reaction mixture with water. It crystallises from alcohol in stout prisms, m.p. 103°. (Found: N, 4.97. $C_{13}H_{13}O_5N$ requires N, 5.32 per cent).

3 : 4 : 5-*Trimethoxy-2-phenylacetic Acid*.—The foregoing cyanomethyl phthalide (5 g.) was refluxed with 10% caustic soda solution (100 c.c.) for 8-9 hours, when evolution of ammonia ceased and the hydrolysis was complete. The product of hydrolysis was then separated by acidification with hydrochloric acid and boiling for 10 minutes, cooling and filtering. The filtered solid was then triturated in a mortar with sodium bicarbonate solution, the solution filtered and the filtrate acidified with excess of hydrochloric acid. It was then crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 126°. (Found: C, 55.08; H, 5.13. $C_{13}H_{14}O_7$ requires C, 55.31; H, 4.96 per cent).

Myristicinic Acid Series.

3 : 4- (or 4 : 5)-*Methylenedioxy-5- (or 3)-methoxy-2-chloromethyl phthalide*.—Myristicinic acid (10 g.), glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.),

fuming hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.) and 40% formaldehyde solution (12.5 c.c.) were mixed together and heated on a steam-bath for 3-4 hours, animal charcoal was then added and heating continued for another $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the solution was then filtered when the product of the reaction crystallised out. It was collected, washed with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and finally crystallised from alcohol in slightly brownish needles, m.p. 133° - 134° . (Found: Cl, 13.59. $C_{11}H_9O_5Cl$ requires Cl, 13.84 per cent).

Cyanomethyl-phthalide.—The above chloromethyl phthalide (5 g.), potassium cyanide (1.5 g.) and alcohol (5 c.c.) were mixed together and heated under reflux on a steam-bath for 3-4 hours and then the product of the reaction was mixed with water, cooled and filtered. The cyanomethyl derivative, thus obtained, was then crystallised from benzine mixed with a little benzene in beautiful woolly needles, m.p. 146° - 47° . (Found: N, 5.74. $C_{12}H_9O_5N$ requires N, 5.66 per cent).

Phenylacetic Acid.—The above cyanomethyl phthalide (5 g.) was boiled under reflux with 10% caustic soda solution (100 c.c.) till there was no evolution of ammonia. The product of hydrolysis was then acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid (75 c.c.) and boiled for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and cooled when the phenyl acetic acid derivative was precipitated. The precipitate was then dissolved in dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, filtered and the filtrate acidified with hydrochloric acid. It was then collected and crystallised from alcohol in prismatic needles, m.p. 211° - 12° . (Found: C, 53.86; H, 4.02. $C_{12}H_{10}O_7$ requires C, 54.13; H, 3.75 per cent).

Phthalide from Myristicinic Acid.—Myristicinic acid (10 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c.c.), formaldehyde (40%, 12.5 c.c.) and water (50 c.c.) were boiled under reflux for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour when a tarry product was found to adhere to the walls of the vessel. The clear liquid was decanted and the tarry product was repeatedly extracted with boiling water, when the phthalide separated on cooling. It was filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from alcohol in stout needles, m.p. 181° . (Found: C, 57.62; H, 4.13. $C_{10}H_8O_5$ requires C, 57.69; H, 3.84 per cent).

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